

Statistical Analysis Plan for the DEXSLEEP study: a single-centre randomised controlled trial to assess whether overnight dexmedetomidine during the first night postoperatively improves early quality of recovery following thoracoscopic lung surgery in older adult patients.

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Section 1: Administrative information

1. Title and Trial registration

Statistical analysis plan for the DEXSLEEP trial: an investigator-initiated, single-center, parallel-group, double blind randomised controlled trial evaluating the effect of overnight dexmedetomidine on early quality of recovery in older adult patients (aged ≥ 60 years) undergoing thoracoscopic lung surgery.

The trial was registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT06480539) on April 11, 2024.

2. SAP Version

Version: 1.0

Date: 15 JUN 2026

3. Protocol Version

This document has been written based on information contained in the study protocol version V1.2, dated 27 March 2024.

4. SAP Revisions – revision history, with justification and timing

Protocol version	Updated SAP version no.	Section number changed	Description of and reason for change	Data changed

Section 2: Introduction

5. Background and rationale

Many patients suffer from pain, fatigue, reduced general well-being, and cognitive dysfunction in the aftermath of major surgery. Another common concern after surgery is sleep impairment and there is little known about its effect on postoperative morbidity, especially postoperative fatigue and muscle function. Dexmedetomidine has been shown to possibly improve postoperative sleep quality in critically ill patients. However, whether the administration of dexmedetomidine translates into reduced postoperative fatigue and/or weakness and improved enhanced recovery after surgery by improving sleep is currently unknown.

6. Objectives

Study objective

The main objective of this prospective clinical trial is to evaluate the effect of the nocturnal administration of dexmedetomidine during the first night after surgery on postoperative recovery in patients aged 60 years or older undergoing thoracoscopic lung surgery.

Research hypothesis

We hypothesise that the nocturnal administration of dexmedetomidine during the first night after surgery improves quality of recovery, as measured by QoR-15. To investigate potential underlying mechanisms, we will also investigate sleep quality and markers of inflammation.

Section 3: Trial Methods

7. Trial design – description of trial design

This trial is a well-controlled, investigator-initiated, single-center, parallel-group, double blind randomised controlled trial with a 1:1 allocation ratio comparing dexmedetomidine with placebo.

8. Randomisation

Randomisation was performed using a computer-generated sequence with a 1:1 allocation ratio. Randomisation was performed with stratification by sex (male or female), age (60-70) or > 70 years), and preoperative use of sleep medication (e.g., z-drugs, benzodiazepines) (yes or no). A computer-generated block randomisation sequence (Castor EDC®) with variable block sizes of 4, 6, and 8 was used. Allocation concealment was ensured using a web-based system (Castor EDC®). Further details have been provided in the clinical trial protocol.

9. Sample size

The sample size was calculated based on the primary outcome (QoR-15 score on POD1), based on a similar patient cohort in the CORTERAS study, we assumed a decrease of 23% in the total QoR-15 score when the questionnaire is completed on POD1 as compared to the preoperative score. Preoperatively, we observed a mean score of 132 (SD 13), which decreased on POD1 to a mean score of 102 (SD 18). Since we expect that the nocturnal administration of dexmedetomidine during the first night will positively impact recovery, we powered the study to find a clinically relevant effect of decreasing this decrease by one third or 33%, namely to a 15% decrease in QoR-15 score on POD1, as such resulting in an anticipated QoR-15 score of 112 (SD 18). With a two-sided α of 0.05, and a power of 80%, we need 102 patients, 51 patients in each study arm.

10. Framework

This trial was designed within a superiority framework, aiming to determine whether the intervention leads to improved outcomes compared with the control group on POD1.

The primary outcome (QoR-15 score on POD1) will be analysed to assess whether the intervention is superior to the control in terms of quality of recovery.

All secondary outcomes, including sleep-related measures (CSD, PSQI, RCSQ, EEG-derived sleep parameters), functional recovery (TUG, HGS), fatigue (CFQ, VAS-F), cognitive outcomes (3D-CAM, TICS), and clinical outcomes (pain scores, PONV), will also be analysed under a superiority framework to evaluate whether the intervention results in improved postoperative recovery, sleep, functional, and clinical status. P-values will be reported, but the results cannot be used for hypothesis testing since the study was not statistically powered to detect differences in the secondary outcomes and since no correction for multiple testing will be done.

Tertiary and safety outcomes, including length of stay (LOS) and adverse events, will be summarised descriptively.

No equivalence or non-inferiority hypotheses are specified for any outcomes.

11. Statistical Interim analyses and stopping guidance

No interim analysis or formal stopping rules were planned regarding the DEXSLEEP study.

12. Timing of final analysis

All outcomes will be analysed collectively after completion of data collection and database lock, and prior to unblinding of treatment allocation.

13. Timing of outcome assessments

Outcome assessments will be performed at predefined time points as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 – outcome assessments DEXSLEEP trial

	Pre-operative	Post-operative	Night after surgery	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Postoperative visit surgeon	Day 28
Timed Up and Go	✓				✓	✓		
Handgrip strength	✓			✓	✓	✓		
EEG reading			✓					
<u>Questionnaires</u>								
Frailty	✓							
Chalder Fatigue	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓
Fatigue VAS scale	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓
QoR-15	✓			✓	✓	✓		
EQ5D	✓							✓
MCTQ	✓							
PSQI	✓							✓
RCSQ				✓				
3D-CAM				✓	✓	✓		
TICS-40	✓							✓
Blood sample	✓	✓	✓ ✓	✓			✓	
Spot urine sample				✓				
Consensus Sleep Diary	<i>daily – starting 3 days before surgery until 7 days after surgery</i>							

Section 4: Statistical Principles

14. Confidence intervals and p-values

All applicable statistical tests will be two-sided and will be performed using a 5% significance level.

All confidence intervals presented will be 95% and two-sided.

15. Adherence and Protocol Deviations

Non-adherence to the intervention is defined as any randomised patient who does not receive the allocated investigational medicinal product (IMP) after randomisation.

Reasons for non-adherence may include: withdrawal of consent after randomisation but before administration of the IMP, clinical decision by the treating physician to withhold the IMP for safety reasons (e.g., postoperative bradycardia or other adverse events posing a contraindication for dexmedetomidine), or change in surgical procedure after randomisation (e.g., conversion from thoracoscopy to thoracotomy), resulting in ineligibility for continued study participation according to protocol-defined inclusion criteria.

In all cases of non-adherence, no IMP will be administered. Protocol deviations will be recorded and documented in accordance with GCP standards.

16. Analysis populations

A modified intention-to-treat (mITT) principle will be applied. The mITT population will include all randomised patients who received IMP. Patients who had been randomised but did not receive the IMP will be excluded from the mITT population and described separately in the CONSORT flow diagram, including reasons for exclusion.

A detailed overview of post-randomisation exclusions will be provided in the CONSORT diagram.

Section 5: Trial Population

17. Screening Data

Screening data will be summarised to describe the representativeness of the enrolled trial population. All patients screened for eligibility and fulfilling the inclusion criteria will be documented in a screening log, including: number of patients eligible, number of patients excluded, and reasons for exclusion according to predefined exclusion criteria.

The screening process will be presented in a CONSORT flow diagram, showing the number of eligible patients screened, excluded (with reasons), randomised, and included in the analysis population.

18. Eligibility

To be eligible to participate in this study, a subject must meet all of the following criteria:

- aged 60 years or older;
- scheduled for thoracoscopic lung surgery.

A potential subject who meets any of the following criteria will be excluded from participation in this study:

- lack of informed consent or inability to give informed consent;
- ≥ 2 nd-degree AV-block without pacemaker;
- uncontrolled hypotension (blood pressure < 90/60 mmHg);
- known hypersensitivity to dexmedetomidine or to any of the excipients;
- acute cerebrovascular conditions;
- urgent, not elective surgery.

The number of ineligible patients randomised, if any, will be reported, with reasons for ineligibility.

19. Recruitment

A CONSORT flow diagram will be used to summarise the number of patients assessed for eligibility, excluded (with reasons), consented, randomised, allocated to each treatment group, who received the allocated intervention, and who withdrew or were lost to follow-up.

20. Withdrawal/follow-up – level of withdrawal

The level of consent withdrawal will be tabulated (classified as “withdrawal of consent before administration of IMP with complete study withdrawal”, “consent to continue follow-up and data collection”, “consent to continue data collection only”, “complete with no further follow-up or data collection”).

Timing of withdrawal will be presented in the CONSORT flow diagram format, with numbers and reasons for withdrawal and/or exclusion from analysis given at each stage/moment. The numbers (with reasons) of losses to follow-up (drop-outs and withdrawals) over the course of the trial will be summarised by treatment arm.

21. Baseline patient characteristics

Patients will be described with respect to age, sex, BMI, ASA class, comorbidities, chronic use of sleep medication and/or pain medication, history of sleep apnoea, and clinical frailty scale at baseline, both overall and separately for each treatment group.

Categorical data will be summarised by numbers and percentages. Continuous data will be summarised by mean and SD if normally distributed and median and IQR if data are skewed. Tests of statistical significance will not be undertaken for baseline characteristics, rather the clinical importance of any imbalance will be noted.

Section 6: Analysis

22. Outcome definitions

Outcomes will be organised according to a predefined hierarchy to reflect their relative importance in the statistical analysis:

- Primary outcome: Quality of recovery, assessed using the Quality of Recovery-15 (QoR-15) score
- Secondary outcomes (Level 1): Sleep-related outcomes
- Secondary outcomes (Level 2): Functional, Cognitive, and Clinical Outcomes
- Tertiary and Safety outcomes: Additional exploratory outcomes and safety assessments

Primary Outcome

The primary outcome is quality of recovery on postoperative day 1 (POD1), measured using the Quality of Recovery-15 (QoR-15) score, a validated patient-reported measure of postoperative recovery, ranging from 0 to 150, with higher scores indicating better quality of recovery.

Secondary Sleep Outcomes

Sleep outcomes are evaluated using both subjective and objective measures. Sleep patterns are assessed using the Consensus Sleep Diary (CSD), completed daily from three days before surgery until seven days after surgery, allowing evaluation of the midpoint of sleep, sleep duration, sleep onset and offset, sleep latency, and inertia.

Baseline sleep-wake characteristics are determined using the Munich ChronoType Questionnaire (MCTQ).

Subjective sleep quality is assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), taken preoperatively and again on POD28. The PSQI consists of 19 items that assess different components of sleep, including sleep latency, sleep duration, sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleep medication, and daytime dysfunction due to poor sleep quality. Each item is rated on a scale from 0 to 3, with higher scores indicating worse sleep quality. The scores from all 19 items are summed to calculate a total score ranging from 0 to 21, with higher scores indicating poorer sleep quality.

Sleep quality during the first postoperative night is specifically evaluated using the Richards-Campbell Sleep Questionnaire (RCSQ). The RCSQ consists of a series of questions (five items) that ask individuals to rate various aspects of their sleep experience. Respondents rate each item on a visual analog scale (0-10) and a total score (0-100) will be calculated with higher scores indicating better sleep quality.

In addition, EEG recordings are obtained during the first postoperative night with a wearable headband (ZMax® device) to provide objective measures of sleep stages.

Secondary Functional, Cognitive, and Clinical Outcomes

Quality of recovery is further evaluated using the QoR-15 score at POD3 and POD5, if the patient was still hospitalised.

The Chalder Fatigue Questionnaire (CFQ) is used to assess fatigue on POD1, POD3, POD5, and POD28. The questionnaire consists of 11 items that assess both physical and mental aspects of fatigue. Respondents rate each item ranging from 0 to 3, the scores are then totaled to provide a measure of overall fatigue (Likert method; 0-33), with a higher score meaning more severe fatigue. To assess fatigue more in detail, the Fatigue-VAS (F-VAS) scale is taken on POD1, POD3, POD5, and POD28. The F-VAS will be subdivided into a fatigue score (0-10, with a higher sum score indicating more fatigue) and an energy score (0-10, with a higher sum score indicating more energy).

Functional recovery is assessed by measuring muscle strength and physical ability, using the Timed Up and Go (TUG) test on POD3 and POD5, as well as handgrip strength (HGS) measurement of the dominant hand on POD1, POD3, and POD5, measured as the percentage decrease from baseline. HGS measurement will be performed with patients seated, elbow flexed at 90°, and repeated three times. The maximal value of the three attempts will be used. The tests are only performed if the patient is still in the hospital.

Cognitive outcomes include the assessment of postoperative delirium (yes/no) using the 3-minute Confusion Assessment Method on POD1, POD3, and POD5. Cognitive function will be evaluated using the Telephone Interview for Cognitive Status (TICS) on POD28. The TICS is comprised of 9 items that result in a maximum score of 40, with higher scores indicating better cognitive function. A cut-off value of 29 indicates mild cognitive impairment, and a cut-off value of 26 indicates cognitive impairment.

Health-related quality of life at POD28 is evaluated using the EQ-5D-5L questionnaire and the EQ-VAS, with index values calculated using the Belgian value set. EQ-5D provides a simple descriptive profile and a single index value for health status, both can be used to assess overall health. The descriptive profile consists of five dimensions: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression. Each dimension has 5 levels of severity: no problems, slight problems, moderate problems, severe problems, or not able. Respondents select the level that best describes their current health status. The EQ-5D also includes a VAS where respondents rate their current health status on a scale from 0 to 100, with 0 being the worst imaginable health state and 100 being the best imaginable health state.

All questionnaires on POD28 were administered by telephone.

Clinical outcomes include postoperative pain, measured using a numeric rating scale (NRS) (0-10) twice daily at 8 a.m. and 6 p.m. until POD3, and the occurrence of postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) during the first postoperative day (yes/no).

Tertiary and safety outcomes

Tertiary and safety outcomes include in-hospital length of stay (LOS) and in-hospital adverse events within 28 days after surgery, including cardiovascular and cerebrovascular events, pulmonary complications, infections, acute kidney injury (KDIGO criteria), and 28-day postoperative mortality.

23. Analysis methods

All analyses will be conducted according to the modified intention-to-treat (mITT) principle. The mITT population will include all randomised patients who received the intervention and completed the primary outcome (QoR-15 questionnaire on POD1).

All statistical tests will be two-sided, and a P value < 0.05 will be considered statistically significant. Effect estimates will be reported with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Only the primary endpoint will be used for hypothesis testing. As there will be no adjustment for multiplicity, all other endpoints will be considered exploratory and hypothesis-generating.

To describe the study population, characteristics of the patients will be presented for each treatment group. Continuous variables will be summarised as mean (standard deviation (SD)) for normally distributed data or median (interquartile range ([IQR]) for non-normally distributed data. Categorical variables will be summarised as counts and percentages. No formal statistical testing of baseline differences will be performed.

Primary outcome analysis

The primary statistical analysis in the DEXSLEEP study will be a modified intention-to-treat analysis.

The treatment effect for the primary outcome will be evaluated by means of a linear mixed model. The statistical model will include:

- Fixed effect for treatment
- Fixed effect for time (defined as categorical, first follow-up measurement after intervention is the reference)
- Fixed effect for the interaction between treatment and time
- Fixed effect for the baseline value of the QoR-15 score
- Fixed effect for the baseline value of PSQI score
- Random intercept for each patient to account for the dependency of the repeated observations within the individual.

The primary hypothesis concerns the treatment contrast at POD 1. This contrast will be estimated from the linear mixed model reported above and fitted to all available repeated measurements. Results will be presented as the number of patients included in the analysis, mean, and 95% CI by treatment group, the estimated treatment effect, a 95% CI for the estimated treatment effect, and a P value.

Adjusting for baseline sleep quality (PSQI) reduces residual variance and accounts for potential imbalance in preoperative sleep quality between groups, independent of randomisation.

Model assumptions will be investigated by means of diagnostics plots. If model assumptions are violated, appropriate remedial measures will be applied.

Secondary outcome analyses

Longitudinal outcomes assessed at POD1, POD3, and POD5, including QoR-15 score, CFQ-11 score, F-VAS score subscale fatigue and energy, TUG, and decrease in HGS, will be analysed using linear mixed-effects models. Fixed effects will include treatment group, time point, and the interaction between treatment group and time point. Baseline values of the respective outcomes and baseline PSQI score will be included as covariates when appropriate. A patient-specific random intercept will be included to account for within-subject correlation. Estimated marginal means and treatment effects over time with 95% CIs will be reported. For each secondary outcome, the adjusted treatment effects at individual postoperative follow-up time points will be evaluated.

Consensus Sleep Diary (CSD) parameters will be analysed using linear mixed-effects models with repeated measures, covering the full assessment window from 3 days before surgery to 7 days after surgery. Fixed effects will include treatment group, time point, treatment-by-time interaction, and baseline values derived from the MCTQ. A patient-specific random intercept will be included to account for within-subject correlation. Estimated marginal means and treatment effects over time with 95% CIs will be reported. Slice estimates will be used to estimate treatment effects at individual postoperative time points.

RCSQ score at POD1 will be analysed using ANCOVA adjusted for baseline PSQI score.

EEG-derived sleep measures obtained from the ZMax[®] device during the first postoperative night will be used to derive objective sleepstage data. Since recordings are only available for the first postoperative night, all EEG-derived parameters will be analysed as single time point outcomes and compared between treatment groups using ANCOVA, adjusted for baseline PSQI score.

The incidence of postoperative delirium assessed with the 3D-CAM will be compared between groups using Fisher's exact test.

Total TICS score at POD28 will be analysed using ANCOVA adjusted for baseline TICS score. For mild cognitive impairment (cut-off value ≤ 29) and cognitive impairment (cut-off value ≤ 26), logistic regression analyses will be performed, adjusting for baseline TICS score. Results will be reported as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% CIs and associated p-values.

All outcomes assessed at POD28, including EQ5D5L index score, EQ5D5L VAS score, CFQ-11 score, PSQI score, will be analysed using ANCOVA with adjustment for respective baseline values.

Pain scores (NRS) and incidence of PONV will be compared between groups using parametric or nonparametric methods as appropriate based on distributional assumptions. Categorical outcomes will be compared using the χ^2 test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate.

Tertiary and safety outcome analyses

Hospital LOS will be summarised as median [IQR].

In-hospital adverse events and 28-day mortality will be summarised descriptively as numbers with percentages.

24. Missing data

The proposed statistical models assume the missing data mechanism to be missing at random (MAR). If missing data are present in either the primary outcome or any of the covariates used in the primary

outcome analysis, a sensitivity analysis will be conducted by means of multiple imputation to assess the robustness of the analysis for the primary outcome.

25. Additional analyses

No subgroup analyses are planned.

No interim analyses are planned.

26. Harms

Adverse events (AEs) and serious adverse events (SAEs) occurring during the study period will be summarised descriptively by treatment group.

27. Statistical Software

All statistical analyses will be performed using JMP Pro (SAS Institute).